

Music Recommendations

This survey is used for evaluation and analysis of music recommendation systems within the Data Science course at TU Wien.

Interpersonal recommendations

Have you ever received music recommendations from friends or acquaintances? *

Yes

No

Interpersonal recommendations - Details

You have received music recommendations through the "interpersonal channel" from friends or acquaintances. Please answer the following questions regarding these recommendations.

Is the music recommended through the channel consistent with the context and theme of your playlist(s)?

1 2 3 4 5

strongly disagree strongly agree

Does the music recommended through the channel diversify category or mood of your playlist(s)?

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree

Is the music recommended through the channel new or novel (recommending previously unknown items)?

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree

Is the music recommended through the channel unexpected but good in terms of the context and theme of your playlist(s)?

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	strongly agree

How often do you receive music recommendations through the channel?

- Hardly ever
- At least once per year
- At least once per month
- At least once per week
- Daily

How convenient is the process of listening to the music recommended through the channel?

- Very inconvenient
- Inconvenient
- Neutral
- Convenient
- Very Convenient

What percentage of the recommended music through the channel is added to your playlist(s)? (please enter a number between 0-100)

70

Non-interpersonal recommendations

Have you ever received new music updates/recommendations from recommendation systems (youtube, spotify, music player, etc)? *

- Yes
- No

Non-interpersonal recommendations - Details

You have received music recommendations through the "non-interpersonal channel" from recommender systems. Please answer the following questions regarding these recommendations.

Is the music recommended through the channel consistent with the context and theme of your playlist(s)?

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree

Does the music recommended through the channel diversify category or mood of your playlist(s)?

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree

Is the music recommended through the channel new or novel (recommending previously unknown items)?

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree

Is the music recommended through the channel unexpected but good in terms of the context and theme of your playlist(s)?

	1	2	3	4	5	
strongly disagree	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	strongly agree

How often do you receive music recommendations through the channel?

- Hardly ever
- At least once per year
- At least once per month
- At least once per week
- Daily

How convenient is the process of listening to the music recommended through the channel?

- Very inconvenient
- Inconvenient
- Neutral
- Convenient
- Very Convenient

What percentage of the recommended music through the channel is added to your playlist(s)? (please enter a number between 0-100)

60

Participant information

Please choose your gender *

- Male
- Female

How old are you? (please enter a number) *

26

What is your geographic group? *

- Asia Pacific
- Europe
- Latin America
- Middle East/Africa
- North America
- Others

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